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INTERPRETATION FEATURES OF RESEARCH RESULTS CONDUCTED WITH AUTONOMOUS DEVICES ON DRILL PIPES IN HORIZONTAL AND SIDE-HOLE WELL SECTIONS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the differences in the interpretation of research data performed in wells with a drill pipe and a logging cable. The influence of the shape of the wellbore, surrounding rocks, the degree of mineralization of the drilling fluid and other factors on various geophysical methods was analyzed.

Keywords: logging, autonomous device, horizontal well, cavernosity, degree of mineralization of the drilling fluid, electromagnetic methods, surrounding rocks.

Research performed in horizontal (HW) and side-hole (SB) wells are elements of modern technology that provide accurate information. Research conducted in HW and SL are the same as the standard methods and complexes applied in vertical wells. Standard methods are often used in the interpretation methodology. However, during the interpretation of the geophysical data obtained by HW, it is necessary to take into account the anisotropy of the layers in its wellbore section, the effect of the wellbore, the opening of layers lying at different angles, etc. It is necessary to take into account such numerous influencing factors.

In this regard, the article attempts to answer some of the questions that a specialist-interpreter often encounters when making decisions based on complex interpretation data obtained directly by autonomous devices in HW and SB.

Analysis of its accuracy in depth measurement and applied methods

Experience shows that in HW and SB, geophysical data obtained by autonomous devices in compliance with the procedure for conducting GWL, data from cable survey methods, as well as lithological studies during drilling, agree well in depth.

When perfect preparation work is not carried out for logging in the wellbore, problems begin to arise,

when the device is raised (lowered) together with the drilling tool occurs at an uneven speed. It is also accompanied by jerks, loss of connection with the device and an increase in the speed of movement. Since the various logging modules included in the AML "HORIZONT" complex are located at different distances from each other, one method passes the research area at different speeds. In such cases, there is no connection between the curves of the methods carried out in one complex, and the inconsistency of the data obtained along the wellbore is also observed at depth. Figure 1 shows an example of curves measured in the same well with the same set of devices at different times before and after the well operation. The difference before and after operation is clearly visible: The appearance of the high-frequency induction logging (HFI) diagrams is stepped, it is clearly visible that they do not coincide with the GK diagrams. During pull-ups, short-term stops of the device can be observed (these are marked in the diagram as steps). This is due to the fact that, despite the continued extension of the cable at the wellhead, the device stops during pull-ups. Since the depth is measured at the wellhead, it is impossible to track the stops and exclude them from the curve registration.

Figure 1. Example of diagrams recorded at different times before and after the operation of a horizontal well (HW)

Thus, one of the main advantages of the autonomous complex (such as the perfect connection of all methods among themselves) is lost. The interpreter has to move all methods relative to each other on the diagram, trying to connect them with each other. According to the electrometry and HFIL methods, a problem arises for qualitative assessment of specific resistance, as well as for providing other petrophysical characteristics of the section.

Differences detected during measurement of zenith and azimuth angles by telemetry and logging

The main and most frequently observed reason for the difference in angles is the non-connection of their inclinometry data. In the event that the methods in the autonomous device are connected to each other at the same measurement point, it can be said with certainty that the corresponding values of the zenith and azimuth angles refer to the same point of the geological section (or the collector layer is detected at this angle).

A description of the comparison of inclinometry data with any method in the complex (usually with the GL curve) is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Example of comparison of AML “HORIZON” measurements with telemetry data

When matching the depths of the GK curve and the zenith angle measured by AML “HORIZON” during telemetric measurements, it turns out that the telemetry data is located 4.5 m above. In this interval, angles of 1-1.50 are intensively recorded, and as a result, the difference increases to 5 m.

The failure of newly drilled wells to reach the bottom hole point expected in the project, i.e. the productive layer, using the logging data measured in the well drilled before operation, leads to a large error and undesirable results. As a result, the drilled wellbore is directed below the water-oil contact (WOC), i.e. it does not enter the expected layer.

Recently, the customer does not order inclinometry measurements during the implementation of the GWL complex, but relies on telemetry

measurements without geophysical control. Such an approach to one of the main methods in HW can lead to large economic costs.

Influence of surrounding rocks on the indicators of various methods

Depending on the trajectory of the wellbore, its profile and spatial location, the results of one or another method will be affected by the anisotropy of the formation or the surrounding rocks, which leads to errors in interpretation. As a rule, the results of induction logging methods are more affected (IL, HFIL).

This is due to the fact that in induction logging methods, the current force lines intersect several layers with different specific resistivities (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Differences in measurement physics between electrical (AR) and electromagnetic (IL) methods

It is clear that even high-Ohm layers in thin layers lead to a decrease in the induced current and, as a result, an increase in the resistance of the environment (sometimes many times).

This effect is also manifested in acoustic methods. In RL methods (GK, 2NNL-I), the surrounding rocks will practically not affect them, since the depth of the investigation is small. Due to the complexity of the problem posed and the impossibility of taking into

account all factors, it is difficult to quantitatively assess these effects. However, the ability to correctly determine in the data obtained whether the anisotropy of rocks affects the indicators of the methods helps to provide a qualitative result. Figure 4 shows an example of the effect of high-Ohm layers on the indicators of the HFL.

Figure 4. Effect of High-Ohm Layers on the HFIL

At first glance, it seems that the HFIL and NNL curves are not connected to each other, and in this case the difference is about 20 m. However, when comparing the trajectory of the well axis with the result obtained from the symmetric gradient probe data during the comprehensive analysis, it becomes clear that this does not depend on the connection of depth at all. It is observed that in the curves obtained with probes with different exploration depths, the top of the layers is recorded at different depths. However, this indicator is more accurate in probes with a small

exploration depth. This is due to the fact that in the probe with a large exploration depth, the top of the layer boundaries is recorded at a depth of 1440 m (absolute depth 1281.2 m), and the bottom is recorded at 1457 m (absolute depth 1282.4 m). The difference in absolute depths is generally 1.2 m, which is acceptable for a 2 m deep-sea survey.

Another example of the effect of a straight boundary on the data of the IL method is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Example of the influence of a straight boundary on the data of the IR method

High-Ohm sandstone layers are located at the top and bottom of the clay layer in the depth interval of 2765-2775 m. The wellbore intersects the layers at a very small angle, and the thickness of the clay layer is only 0.65 m vertically. Since the depth of the IR probe is 1 m, high resistivity is recorded due to the influence of the surrounding high-Ohm layers, which is not observed in the measurement work with a gradient probe.

In addition to the inaccurate determination of the boundary of the layers, a more serious problem in such cases is the high resistivity of the layer due to the influence of the surrounding rock. In most cases, this type of dense rocks is present at the top or bottom of the projected layer. As a rule, the wellbore intersects the designed horizon at a small angle, and the influence of dense rocks causes an error in determining the saturation of the layer (an aquifer can be considered oil-bearing, an oil-bearing layer gas-bearing, etc.).

The influence of wellbore diameter on the results of geophysical methods

Currently, since the complex geophysical methods conducted in HW and SB do not include EL, SL and

profiler methods, it is very difficult to give a qualitative result unambiguously and correctly.

Firstly, as mentioned above, the anisotropy of rocks has a significant effect on induction methods, and as a result, it becomes difficult to correctly separate formations, select collector layers, and also correctly assess saturation.

Secondly, in a horizontal wellbore, the diameter of the well is not classical, that is, a cavern is observed in front of clay layers, a nominal diameter in dense rocks, and a narrowing of the well wall in collectors. This is due to the different technological processes used during drilling and wellbore flushing, as well as the trajectory of the wellbore.

Figure 6 shows a fragment of the well profile. Thin lines are the trajectory of the ax during well flushing. Such technological cavities are formed during well flushing and can be observed anywhere in the wellbore, depending on the open wellbore section. Therefore, during drilling, it is necessary to know the diameter of the well in front of the intended collector in advance so that it can be taken into account in the calculation of petrophysical data.

Figure 6. The nature of cavities formed in non-typical places of HW

The change in the diameter of the well has a significant impact on the performance of electrical methods. Observations show that in high-Ohm carbonate sections drilled with a saline-based solution, a change in the diameter of the well by even 1 mm leads to a significant (sometimes multiple) difference in the calculated value of the specific resistivity (AR).

Some features of the diagrams of electromagnetic methods

The HFIL and low-frequency IR used when exploring wells in terrigen sections (low Ohm) often do not give good results when exploring inclined and horizontal wells drilled in high-Ohm sections.

First, when drilling horizontal wells, polymer and saline drilling fluids are more often used, which significantly reduce the upper limit of the measured AR

value of rocks. The technical specification of the HFIL states that when the resistance of the drilling fluid is 1 Ohm, there is no error in the measured resistance value up to 200 Ohm. Accordingly, when the specific resistance of the drilling fluid is 0.1 Ohm, this value decreases accordingly and becomes 20 Ohm.

Secondly, in the immediate vicinity of the productive layer in multilayer sections, or in the longitudinal direction of its coverage, at the layer boundary, there are high-Ohm layers that significantly affect the HFIL method.

Thirdly, experience shows that the IR indicator is significantly affected by changes in the well profile. Figure 7 shows an example of a low-frequency IR curve in a carbonate section.

Figure 7. Example of indicators of complex methods in carbonate section

At first glance, without comparing the IR curve with other methods, one can conclude that the device is not working properly. It seems that the sinusoidal curves obtained from the influence of an “undesirable frequency” or damage to the cable are well visible. However, this is not possible in autonomous devices released from inside the pipes, and curves of such a nature are formed as a result of the spiral shape of the well profile. Such a well profile has a strong influence on almost all methods, including 2NNL-I, GGL-S, GP, etc. methods.

Compared with RL and AR, it is sometimes not possible to divide the section into lithotypes according to IR. This is due to the fact that the well was drilled with a solution with a high degree of mineralization, and the dynamic indicator of IR is not sufficient to select layers with high specific resistance. It is impossible to use these data in both qualitative and quantitative interpretation. Under such conditions, these methods are not considered informative and do not provide any assistance to the interpreter. In most cases, the customer orders the methods of inertial and geotechnical survey (GTS) in wells drilled with vertical and non-permeable solutions. In wells drilled with solutions with high mineralization, the quality of electromagnetic methods is significantly reduced, even in small Ohm sections. Therefore, it is important to use complex methods. In addition to induction methods, it

is recommended to record the curves of the SL and symmetrical gradient probes (GZ-S).

Features of WP measurements

When logging with autonomous devices from inside the pipes, the conditions in the wellbore have a strong influence on the WP indicator. When lowering the drill pipes together with the devices, a “piston effect” occurs, which creates conditions for an increase in pressure in the wellbore. In reservoir layers with high filtration and capacity properties (good permeability), this pressure drop causes the absorption of drilling fluid. It is known that the self-generated polarization potential consists not only of diffusion and diffusion-adsorption potentials, but also of percolation potentials. As a result, any fluid flow from the wellbore to the formation or vice versa will negatively affect the result of the WP indicators. This percolation feature can be misleading. For example, in a freshwater-based solution, the WP and GL data should be similar. However, when the wellbore intersects high-permeability layers, the opposite effect can be observed, that is, while the WP and GL in the clays are similar, a high positive WP anomaly may arise in front of the reservoir layers. Figure 8 shows the results of comparing the WP curves and GL measured during the lowering and raising of the device in wells drilled with freshwater-based solutions.

Figure 8. Comparison of WP curves measured during lowering and raising of the device according to the state of filtration potential

The figure shows areas where a significant difference is observed in the curves of WP measured during lowering and recorded during lifting. As can be seen, this difference occurs in front of the collector layers and it can be safely assumed that this difference is due to the fluid flow, resulting in the formation of an additional filtration anomaly. Most interpreters try to convert it by considering this as an “inverted” WP field, which is typical for saline solutions. In this case, the expected result is obtained in front of permeable collector layers, but in non-permeable collectors where there is no filtration property, the opposite indicator is obtained.

Based on experience, it can be concluded that the indicators of the WP curve measured inside the pipes are rarely classic. This is due either to the lack of informativeness of the WP curve as a result of the

difference in the degree of mineralization of the liquid in the layer compared to that in the solution, or to the influence of the above-mentioned filtration effect. Therefore, specialists - interpreters have difficulties in selecting reservoir layers, as well as calculating porosity when using this method.

Factors affecting the performance of radioactive logging methods

Numerous analyses of well materials have revealed a number of factors that significantly affect the performance of radioactive methods (2NNL-I, GGL-S). The main of these factors is that, unlike cable-driven devices, autonomous devices are firmly attached to the drill pipes and, depending on the profile of the well, the presence of protrusions, areas with cuttings, a sealed plug, etc., will constantly change their location in the wellbore to the center of the well wall or vice versa.

Naturally, in such cases, changes in the diameter and profile of the well, together with a drilling fluid with a high degree of mineralization, affect the results of radioactive logging methods.

Currently, modeling the position of the device in the borehole and, as a result, correctly applying the correction for the drilling fluid, is complicated. This influence factor can be minimized only by properly preparing the well for drilling, stabilizing the wellbore, and washing the cuttings and packing area.

Figure 9 shows a fragment from a complex study conducted in a wellbore with a specific resistance of the drilling fluid of 0.1 Ohm. In this section, a well-saturated reservoir layer is observed. Based on the

Figure 9. Example of the influence of the well profile on the GGL-S indicators

Conclusion

The results of standard well geophysical survey methods conducted in HW and SB wells can differ significantly from the classical methods observed in vertical wells. This is often due not to the unstable operation of autonomous devices, but to such influencing factors as the anisotropy of the layers intersecting HW and SB, the presence of cuttings in the wellbore, salinization of the drilling fluid, and changes in diameter along the entire wellbore. Poor preparation of the wellbore with improper selection of drilling fluid will lead to stretching of the device, uneven speed of the gauge recording and, as a result, incorrect depth of the layers.

Unfortunately, some drilling companies and major customer organizations neglect well preparation in order to save time; they use solutions that increase the speed of drilling transition, not paying attention to the negative impact on the quality and result of logging.

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GGL-S data without adjusting for the well diameter, the reservoir layer can be interpreted as a layered clay reservoir. The sinusoidal nature of the density (RHOB) curve is not related to the lithology of this layer. Profilometry and radiometry (CALI, R1-R8) data show that the wellbore has a spiral “corrugated” profile. Such a profile has a great influence on the GGL-S and HFIL indicators and is typical for wells drilled by the rotor method.

If there is no profilometry data in the mentioned complex, in such cases many questions arise during interpretation and a large error may occur in the results given.

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